

Investigating the spatial distribution of soil wind-erodible indices using geostatistical methods in the Sistan plain

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Article Info

ABSTRACT

Article type:

Research Article

Article history:

Received: 21 July 2024

Revised: 26 August 2024

Accepted: 10 October 2024

Keywords:

Deltaic Soils, Cokriging, Alluvial Activities, Aeolian Activities.

The study of land erodibility and its spatial modeling is the main and key information for sustainable land management. Wind erosion is one of the main environmental hazards in Sistan region. Therefore, this research aimed to investigate the spatial changes and modeling of wind erodibility indices in the Sistan Plain. For this purpose, 181 points were selected over the plain, and surface soil was sampled. The studied indices included the laboratory wind-erodible fraction (EF), the wind-erodible fraction based on Fryrear formula (EFF), López formula (EFL), Bouajila formula (EFB), soil crust factor (SCF), dry aggregate stability (DAS) and the soil erodibility. Also, some physical and chemical characteristics were measured in soil samples using standard methods. IDW, kriging, and cokriging were used as geostatistical analysis methods. The results showed that the best variogram model for EFF, SCF, EFB, and DAS was the spherical model, and for EFL, EF, and soil erodibility was the exponential model and the spatial fit for all indices was in the average spatial fit class. The best predictive methods were simple cokriging with covariate of sand for EFF (RMSE=5.724) and soil erodibility (RMSE=85.576), with covariate of clay for EFB (RMSE=2.950) and DAS (RMSE=14.481) and with covariate of sand to clay ratio for EF (RMSE=17.966) and ordinary cokriging method for SCF (RMSE=0.163) and EFL (RMSE=36.312) with covariate of sand to clay ratio. The average values of EFF equal to 29.13%, SCF equal to 0.45%, EFL equal to 75.25%, EFB equal to 83.09%, EF equal to 54.97%, DAS equal to 72.18% and soil erosion equal to 121.67 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. The highest values of wind-erodible indices were observed in the southern parts of the Sistan plain, and, the lowest values were observed in the northern and western parts. However, the highest value of DAS was found in the northern and western parts and the lowest in the southern part of the plain. There was a high match between the spatial distribution of erodibility indices and the spatial distribution of soil particle size. The changes in soil mineral particles in the region depend on the geomorphic nature of the region and are in line with the changes in the sedimentation regime of the Hirmand River and its branches, as well as wind erosion and sedimentation processes in the Sistan Plain.

Cite this article: Shahriari, A., Mohammadi, S. M., Shirmohammadi, E., Fatemi Ghomesheh, A., & Galavi, H. (2025). Investigating the spatial distribution of soil wind-erodible indices using geostatistical methods in the Sistan plain. *Journal of Natural Environmental Hazards*, 14(43), 23-28. DOI: 10.22111/jneh.2024.49372.2060

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Publisher: University of Sistan and Baluchestan

DOI: 10.22111/jneh.2024.49372.2060

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most important environmental hazards of arid and desert areas in the world is wind erosion and dust storms as a result. Therefore, the study of land erodibility and its spatial modelling is the main and key information for sustainable land management. One of the new methods of spatial modelling of soil properties is digital soil mapping (DSM), which uses complex models. One of the DSM methods that has been used by researchers for decades is geostatistics. Due to the hyper-arid climate and constant and strong winds known as 120-day winds, wind erosion and dust storms are some of the main environmental hazards in the Sistan region. Therefore, this research was carried out to investigate the spatial changes and modelling of wind erosion indices in the Sistan Plain using geostatistical methods.

DATA AND METHODS

To spatially model the indices of wind erosion, 181 study points in the Sistan plain were selected and their surface soil was sampled. The studied indices included the laboratory wind-erodible fraction (EF), the wind-erodible fraction based on Fryrear formula (EFF), López formula (EFL), Bouajila formula (EFB), soil crust factor (SCF), dry aggregate stability (DAS) and the soil erodibility. Also, 13 physical and chemical characteristics (characteristics related to soil fertility, salinity and sodicity), including percentage of clay, silt, sand (also the ratio of sand to clay), saturated moisture percentage (SP), Electrical conductivity (EC) in saturated extract, soil reaction (pH), percentage of organic matter (OM), soil calcium carbonate equivalent (CCE), cation exchange capacity (CEC), sodium absorption ratio (SAR), available phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) content in soil samples were measured using standard methods. Inverse Distance weighting, Kriging and Cokriging methods were used as geostatistical analysis methods. For each geostatistical method, two simple and ordinary modes were considered, and all the measured soil properties were analyzed as auxiliary variables separately in the Cokriging method. To evaluate the accuracy of the models and choose the best model, the coefficient of explanation (R^2), mean error (ME) and root mean square error (RMSE) were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that the soils of Sistan Plain had a medium to coarse texture with the predominance of sand and silt particles, and they had low fertility and were part of saline and sodic soils. The results showed that the best variogram model for EFF, SCF, EFB and DAS was the spherical model and for EFL, EF and soil erodibility was the exponential model, and the spatial fit for all indices was in the average spatial fit class. The best predictive methods were simple Cokriging with covariate of sand for EFF (RMSE=5.724) and soil erodibility (RMSE=85.576), with covariate of clay for EFB (RMSE=2.950) and DAS (RMSE=14.481) and with covariate of sand to clay ratio for EF (RMSE=17.966) and ordinary cokriging method for SCF (RMSE=0.163) and EFL (RMSE=36.312) with covariate of sand to clay ratio. The average values of EFF equal to 29.13%, SCF equal to 0.45%, EFL equal to 75.25%, EFB equal to 83.09%, EF equal to 54.97%, DAS equal to 72.18% and soil erosion equal to 121.67 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. The highest values of wind-erodible indices were observed in the southern parts of the Sistan plain, and, the lowest values were observed in the northern and western parts. However, the highest value of DAS was found in the northern and western parts and the lowest in the southern part of the plain.

CONCLUSION

In arid areas with significant wind activity, soil wind erodibility indices are very important environmental parameters that can be used for decision-making and land management. The correlation results between the studied wind erodibility indices showed a high correlation of these indices with each other, which shows that the selection of these indices is due to the high correlation regarding the wind erodibility of the soil. The high correlation between EF, DAS and the estimated amount of soil

erosion shows the importance of laboratory indicators in estimating erodibility and matching them with the natural environment. The results showed that the use of environmental variables with the cokriging method to prepare a map of soil wind erodibility indices and their spatial modelling is effective. There was a high match between the spatial distribution of erodibility indices and the spatial distribution of soil particle size (sand, silt and clay). The changes in soil mineral particles in the region depend on the geomorphic nature of the region and are in line with the changes in the sedimentation regime of the Hirmand River and its branches, as well as wind erosion and sedimentation processes in the Sistan Plain. The results of this study can be important and practical for managers, decision-makers and land users in the direction of development and sustainable living.

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